

A CASE STUDY: AYURVEDIC MANAGEMENT OF SHWITRA BY PRACCHANA KARMA AND ARAGWADHADI TAILA

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ABSTRACT

Shwitra is a chronic skin disorder characterized by dry and non-infectious lesions. It presents as whitish discoloration of the skin and can affect individuals of any age group, from children to the elderly, and occurs regardless of gender, religion, socioeconomic status, or age. Vitiligo can be correlated with Shwitra in Ayurveda because both share similar signs and symptoms, such as non-exudative white, red, or coppery-red patches on the skin, along with roughness, dryness, itching, burning sensation, and loss or discoloration of hair in the affected areas. According to Ayurveda, Shwitra results from the vitiation of all three doshas. Pracchana karma is one of the shastrakrita raktamokshana procedures in which multiple small incisions are made to remove impure blood, and it is generally used as a local (sthanika) therapy. In this study, Aragwadhadi taila was applied externally for the management of Shwitra, and

the results obtained were found to be encouraging.

KEYWORDS: Shwitra; pracchana karma; Aragwadhadi taila; vitiligo.

1. INTRODUCTION

Shwitra is a chronic illness. The lesions of shwitra being dry and also non-infectious thus differs from the kushtha in general. It has been described along with kushtha in the classic. It is whitish discoloration of skin starting from child to old, rich to poor, irrespective of sex, religion, status, age. It is common skin disorder, which is correlated with vitiligo to certain extent in contemporary system of medicine. Vitiligo is a non-contagious acquired pigmentation disorder characterized by sharply defined white patches of variable shape and dimensions, increasing in size and number with time. Vitiligo is the most common depigmenting skin disorder, with an estimated prevalence of 0.5–2% of the population in both adults and children worldwide.^[1] Males and females are equally affected, although women and girls often seek consultation more frequently, possibly due to the greater negative social impact than for men and boys.^[2] Vitiligo is a multifactorial disorder characterized by the loss of functional melanocytes.^[3] Multiple mechanisms have been proposed for melanocyte destruction in vitiligo. These include genetic, autoimmune responses, oxidative stress, generation of inflammatory mediators and melanocyte detachment mechanisms. It can be co-related with Shwitra disease in Ayurveda due to the alike signs and symptoms which are; non exudative white, red or coppery-red colored patches, roughness, dryness, itching, burning sensation of the patches, loss and discoloration of the hair.^[4] Shwitra is caused by vitiation all the three doshas. Shwitra is raktapradoshaja vikara and twakagata roga.^[5] The main cause for the disease is believed to be Purva Janma Krita Paapa Phala.^[6] In the case of Shwitra, bhrajaka pitta gets imbalanced and causes depigmentation of skin. Ayurvedic medicine is the best option for balancing for balancing of bhrajaka pitta and samavastha of all three doshas without any side effect.^[7] Prachanna karma is one of among the shastrakrita raktamokshana in which multiple small incisions are made to irrigate the impure blood. It is usually adopted as a sthanik Chikitsa. This case is there to show the effect of pracchana karma followed by Aragwadhadi taila application.

2. BRIEF CASE HISTORY

The patient is a 35-year-old male who first started experiencing depigmentation at age 30 over right cheek. There were 05 patches of white color and irregular margins, having mild itching occasionally on the patches for 02 years. The patient gave history of lesions that initially they were small in size than increase in size gradually. The size measuring up to 1×1 cm², 1×1cm², 1×0.8cm², 0.2×0.2cm², 0.1×0.1cm². Sensation, temperature of the lesions was normal but hair color of the lesions was white. Patient had taken treatment for the vitiligo

from their local hospital, topical creams and steroids were given but he didn't get any relief. Of note is the absence of any family history of vitiligo or autoimmune disorders.

3. AYURVEDIC EXAMINATION

Treatment Plan

After Proper analysis, (blood investigation, coagulopathy, any allergy about serological) patient was planned for pracchana karma once a week for one month with Aragwadhadi taila application.

Procedure

Under all aseptic conditions, patient was made to lie down in suitable position, part preparation done. Local area clean with sprit. Pracchana karma done with 11 number surgical blade, after vertical parallel superficial incisions were made, bloodletting done. Application of Aragwadhadi taila was done for when it was come to dry then wiped out with sterile gauze pieces. Aragwadhadi taila application was done twice a day for one month. And 2 follow up after 15 days in one month.

Assessment Criteria

Healing of shwitra was assessed on the basis of–

1. Color
2. Itching
3. Size

4. OBSERVATION

Regular use of Aragwadhadi taila application with pracchana karma minimized the size and shrinkage of patches. There was color change in patches from white to pink and then normal colour in the whole treatment schedule of 01 months study. And hair color of lesions was also in black color.

5. RESULTS

All the 05 lesions could acquire normal skin colour after one month treatment. In the whole study no internal medicine was done.

- **After treatment**-Number of patches: total 05, healed 05 patches

Table 1: Ashtavidha Pariksha.

S.N	Ashtavidh pariksha	Observation
1.	Naadi	86/minute, Vishama(Vataja)
2.	Mutra	Pramana — 600–800 mL/day, Avritti — Samyaka, Dhara—Prakrit, Varna—Prakrit, Gandha—Prakrit
3.	Mala	Nirama, consistency—semisolid, Varna— Pita, Avrutti—Samyaka
4.	Jihva	Anavruta, Varna—Raktabha
5.	Shabda	Mand
6.	Sparsha	Tvaka—Snigdha
7.	Drika	Drishti—Svabhavika, Varna— Twakvaivarnya (hypo/depigmentation of skin)
8.	Akruti	Krishna

Table 2: Dasavidha Pariksha.

S.N	Dashvidha pariksha	Observations
1.	Prakriti	(a) Sharirika—Kapha-Pittaja (b) Mansika—Rajsika
2.	Vikriti	(a) Dosha—Tridoshaja, (b) Dushya—Rakta, Mamsa, Meda, (c) Adhishtana-Twak, (d) Srotodushti—Vimarga gamana
3.	Sara	Twak Asarata, RaktaAsarata, Mansa Asarata, Meda Asarata, Asthi Sarta, Majja Sarta, Shukra Sarta
4.	Samhanana	Pravara
5.	Pramana	Avara
6.	Satmya	Madhyam
7.	Satva	Avara
8.	Aharashakti	Avara
9.	Vyayam Shakti	Avara
10.	Vaya	Yuvavastha

Color-Dark brown

Itching-Absent

Pathya -Cow milk and ghee, Munga, Patol, Mudga and easily digestive foods were advised.

Apathya -Guda, Tila, Curd, Milk+fruits, Fish, heavy diets etc were avoided.

Table 3: Colour of Patches.

Grade 0	Normal skin color
Grade 1	Brown color
Grade 2	Reddish color
Grade 3	Pink color
Grade 4	White color

Table 4: Size of Patches.

Grade 0	Up to 0.5 cm
Grade 1	0.6 to 01cm
Grade 2	1.1cm to 02 cm
Grade 3	2.1cm to 03 cm
Grade 4	3.1cm to 04 cm
Grade 5	4.1cm to 05cm

Table 5: Itching.

Grade 0	Absent
Grade 1	Mild
Grade 2	Moderate
Grade 3	Severe

6. DISCUSSION

In this study, Aragwadhadi taila is used externally for the management of shwitra, the Result of which has been found encouraging. Shwitra is caused by vitiation of Tridosha and Twacha, Rakta, Mamsa and Lasika as dushya's effecting the bahya roga marga by means of vimarg gaman type of sroto dushti prakara. The treatment protocol as per the classics for any kushtha is shodhan followed by taila application on the lesions. In this case study sthanik shodhana of shwitra lesion was achieved by pracchana karma, as one of the dushya involved in shwitra is rakta dhatu. Further in the context of Taila application Acharya sushrutas advocated application on shwitra should be done only after some lekhana. Hence the pracchana was planned to achieve Bhuta shodhana and lekhana purpose. Followed by Aragwadhadi taila application, to clear the srota sanga and stimulates the melanin secretion by means increased blood circulation. So in shwitra shrotodushti is removed by pracchana karma, as in this, the vitiated blood is irrigated out causing high blood circulation in that area and thus provide nutrition to the cells present there.

Table 6: Before Treatment.

Size of Patches (approx)					
	1	2	3	4	5
Size	1×1 cm	1×1 cm	1×0.8Cm	0.2×0.2Cm	0.1×0.1cm
Colour	4	4	3	4	3
Itching	1	0	1	1	1

Table 7: After Treatment.

Size of Patches					
1	2	3	4	5	
Size	0	0	0	0	0
Colour	0	0	0	0	0
Itching	0	0	0	0	0

BEFORE TREATMENT AFTER TREATMENT

7. CONCLUSION

Based on the observation and results of this single case study it can be concluded that shwitra due to obstructive pathology by means of vitiated tridosha and dushyas like rakta mamsa lasika meda has got remedy in the ayurvedic classics specially with sthanik pracchana karma followed by Aragwadhadi taila application. Result may be achieved in less time duration and with high percentile, if the pracchana karma and Aragwadhadi taila application advocated after classical vaman and virechana. The case demonstrates clinically.

Promising results in Re-pigmentation without any adverse effects. It is also worth noting that new areas of hypopigmentation also did not appear during the treatment.

CONSENT AND ETHICAL APPROVAL

As per international standard or university standard guideline patients consent and ethical approval has been collected and preserved by the authors.

COMPETING INTERESTS

Authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

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